

Synthesis of some Dihydrobenz (1,3) oxazine Derivatives

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The dihydrobenz (1,3) oxazine derivatives (III) are readily accessible through a variant of Mannich reaction from *p*-substituted phenols¹⁻². It has been utilised by several groups of workers³⁻⁶ to prepare bio-active compounds; for instance, a few compounds synthesized from *p*-acetylaminophenol (I) were reported⁵⁻⁶ to possess anti-tumor activities. This prompted us to synthesize a series of III from I as noted below :

In the usual run of the reaction, a mixture of I (0.02m), primary amine (0.02m) and formaldehyde (0.05m) in 50 ml of ethanol was left overnight at room temperature and it was then refluxed over steam bath for 3 hrs. After the removal of ethanol under suction, the residue was extracted with boiling benzene from which the phenolic ingredients were removed with cold 2% aqueous alkali. The dry benzene solution (sod. sulphate) after concentration and dilution with petroleum-ether afforded the desired compounds which could be readily crystallised from appropriate solvents.

The reaction presumably proceeds through formation of the phenolic base (II) as intermediate, but the above procedure was somewhat unsatisfactory with aromatic amines. In the latter instances, when the mixture of amine and formaldehyde was initially refluxed for 2 hr. in *n*-butanol and subsequently heated under refluxing condition (10 hr) after addition of I, the yield was appreciably raised in all cases. Similarly, *n*-hexylamine, provided an alkali insoluble product (which forms an oxalate). This product had the striking property of forming a gel from most of the non-polar solvents and could not be obtained in well defined form.

The properties of the dihydrobenzoxazines (III) are presented in Table 1. The UV absorption pattern is similar in all cases and is characterised by a strong peak around 250 $\mu\mu$

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and a wide band (shoulder) in the 285–295 $m\mu$ region. Inspection of spectral data in Table 1 suggests that when R = aryl, in III, there is an additive effect on the band intensities. Comparison of our data with those of known⁷ benzenoid bands indicates that these are associated with primary (¹La) and secondary (¹Lb) benzenoid bands.

Examination of IR spectra (Nujol) of compounds 4 and 6 (Table 1) revealed near identical absorption pattern and the bands of interest were at : 2.92 μ ; 6.03 μ ; 6.50 μ ; 7.96 μ ; 8.25 μ (No. 4) and 8.32 μ (No. 6).

TABLE 1

Properties of Dihydrobenz (1,3) oxazines (III).

No.	Compd(III) R =	M.P. °C	Crystallising solvent	Yield %	λ_{max}^{EtOH} $m\mu$ ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$)	Molecular formula	% N	
							Required	Found
1.	<i>n</i> -Propyl	112–13	Benzene :	51	251 (13.8)	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	11.96	11.69
			Hexane		~290 (3.0)			
2.	<i>n</i> -Butyl	94–5	„	55	251 (13.9)	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	11.38	11.26
					~290 (3.3)			
3.	Cyclohexyl	138–39 ^a	MeOH	60	253 (13.8)	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.22	10.08
					~292 (3.3)			
4.	Benzyl	166–7 ^b	„	55	250 (13.4)	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	9.93	9.83
					~285 (2.7)			
5.	α -Phenethyl	145	Benzene :	60	253 (13.2)	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	9.46	9.30
			Hexane		~292 (2.7)			
6.	β -Phenethyl	130	„	60	250 (13.0)	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	9.46	9.45
					~285 (2.7)			
7.	Phenyl	177–8	MeOH	70	248 (25.4)	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	10.44	10.14
					~285 (5.0)			
8.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	144–5	„	50	248 (23.6)	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	9.93	9.56
					~284 (4.2)			
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	188–9	„	68	252 (30.5)	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.25	9.04
					~284 (2.7)			
10.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	160–1	„	51	251 (27.6)	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.25	8.97
					~291 (4.9)			
11.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	203–4	Benzene	58	*	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.25	9.22
12.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	140–1	MeOH	30	245 (20.4)	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	8.97	8.79
					~300 (4.7)			

(a) Reported (ref. 6) m.p. 139°

(b) Reported (ref. 2) m.p. 168°

+ Sparingly soluble in alcohol.

The dihydrobenzoxazines are undoubtedly highly sensitive to acid, but their accredited¹ stability under alkaline condition is somewhat at variance with our observation; and we wish to take it up in subsequent communication.

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